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The Importance of Educational Games in Teaching Foreign Languages to Children in Preschool Early: Problems and Solutions

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Abstract: *The process of globalization requires people to learn several foreign languages in addition to their mother tongue. Current research shows that it is more effective to start this process at an early age. In our country, too, special attention is paid to this issue, programs are being developed on the basis of a new approach to teaching foreign languages, especially English, in cooperation with the world's leading organizations and universities. In the last 3 years, this process has been particularly evolving in preschool education. Large-scale projects on teaching English in public and private preschools are being implemented. This article discusses the importance of using educational games in the teaching of foreign languages, especially English, in early childhood, and the ease with which language skills can be easily acquired through a variety of games. Keywords: foreign language, language learning at an early age, educational play, activity, fine motor skills, eye-hand coordination, active learning types, block play in English, role-playing games, manual labor.*

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Today, we all know that the fate of every child is of paramount importance. Speaking about his educational process and scientific potential, he said that in kindergarten and school age, play is the main and favorite hobby of the child, so the child also explores the world through play. . If foreign languages are taught in a mixed way, this will increase the effectiveness of language skills several times. After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. Today, there is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take a worthy place in the world community,

for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. As a logical continuation of this idea, the Presidential Decree of December 10, 2021 "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages.

Play not only increases a child's physical activity but also helps to shape his mental alertness. The game also helps the child to strengthen his self-confidence, to form social relationships with others. For this reason, parents and educators should encourage children to learn through play as much as possible. It is through play that children learn and discover their talents. To achieve this, it is advisable to use an environment that activates the sensory organs, including active forms of education, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic. Educational games include playing musical instruments, singing songs, reciting poems, dancing, playing games, watching videos, and making various things through handicrafts.

➤ **It is preferable to learn foreign languages at what age**

Scientists around the world are unanimous in their view that a child can easily learn a foreign language by the age of 10. During this period, the child learns languages mechanically rather than comprehensively so that the use and pronunciation of a foreign language is easily mastered. But even so, given that a child is born with the ability to imitate the sounds of any language, those who intend to start the process early also make up the majority. Studies of the human brain have shown that the period from birth to the age of three is the most important period of a child's development. It has also been found that the brain of a three-year-old child works twice as fast and better than that of an adult. Therefore, according to British experts, introducing a child to a second language in the first year will help him to master it easily. But in any case, we must not forget that it is extremely important to take into account the child's psychological and language skills.

➤ **Child readiness**

Every child is an individual, of course, their stages of development are also different. According to psychologists, forcing a child to speak at an early age or trying to develop him or her in comparison to his or her peers often has the opposite effect and leads to poor results. Psychological and pedagogical features, ie their curiosity and ambition, should be taken into account when teaching a foreign language to children of kindergarten and primary school age. It is also important to keep in mind that children may not be able to focus on one type of activity for long periods of time. Parents want their child to be mature in all respects, and in many cases, regardless of the child's psychological and physiological readiness, try to give him loads of various subjects, language teaching or sports. In most cases, when parents fail to achieve the expected result, they try to influence the child by reprimanding the child or comparing them to their peers. But both of these attempts weaken the child's motivation to learn and cause him to lose interest in the things around him. The role of parents and caregivers in preventing such tragedies is invaluable. The easiest and most acceptable way to teach a child to think freely, to increase his curiosity and motivation to explore the environment, to enrich the child's imagination, to reveal his creativity is this game. As children play, they put their ideas into practice, test hypotheses, acquire the necessary skills, use their imagination, and explore their own worlds.

➤ **The importance of the game**

The child is very curious by nature and he uses all his senses to explore the world around him. Since play is the most basic and favorite hobby of a child, if the child is introduced to the world around him and all the necessary knowledge and skills in it through play, the effectiveness of mastering the skills

will increase several times. Play not only increases the child's physical activity, but also helps him to form mental alertness. The game also helps the child to build self-confidence, to form social relationships with others. This is why parents and caregivers should encourage children to learn through as much play as possible. It is through play that children learn and discover their talents. To achieve this, it is advisable to use an environment that activates the sensory organs, including active forms of education, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic. Educational games include playing musical instruments, singing songs, reciting poems, dancing, playing games, watching videos, and making various things through handicrafts. Games such as colorful exhibitions, cards, competitions, role-playing games, making different shapes are one of the most fun ways to develop children's physical and mental activities.

➤ **Children both play and develop and learn.**

When playing with plasticine, children develop the skills of "small metrics". When children make shapes in plasticine, the activity of the eyes and hands is coordinated and the muscles of the hands and fingers are strengthened. This, in turn, is one of the most important skills before developing writing skills, as strong muscle strength and "eye-hand coordination" (visual-motor coordination) allow children to hold writing instruments correctly. and helps them use them wisely. By playing with plasticine, children also learn the characteristics of objects, such as color, shape, and structure. In educational activities involving musical instruments, children learn to distinguish different tones. Children begin to understand how the sounds and sounds emanating from different instruments change. The speed and stillness of the musical tone move according to the high and low of the sound curtains.

When playing with transport toys, children move up and down, forward and backward quickly and slowly, testing the force of friction and movement.

As children play with blocks and cubes, they learn the concepts of color, shape, and decoration, as well as weight, size, height, length, vertical, and horizontal.

➤ **Educational activities that encourage children to communicate**

Young children learn through their emotions and actions, so learning English should also be done through these emotional feelings and behaviors. Involving young children in interesting and communicative situations and activities in learning English is a very important factor in mastering language skills.

Although the goal of the activity is to teach English, it can be engaging for children, such as play, and for children to engage in these activities involuntarily and for children to learn a foreign language as naturally as their mother tongue. The provision is also noteworthy.

It is especially important to create a variety of interesting and stimulating situations for young children to learn English and to use all available opportunities to ensure that children actively participate in it.

➤ **Situation / Educational activities**

Since English is at the heart of any situation and activity, it is advisable that these activities be conducted in English in a fluent and understandable manner. It is necessary to shorten the communication in the native language and give the main emphasis to the English language. Of course, one of the first and most important successes in language teaching is the ability of the coach to engage the child with gestures, gestures and fluent speech and tone of speech in English. In particular, language instructors will be introduced to “Playing with blocks or legos”, “Dressing”, “Animals and their sounds”, “Animals and their sounds”.), “Crafts”, Sing a song, etc. are some of the best ways to develop language learning skills in young children. By using these activities, we will have the opportunity to expand and develop children’s vocabulary, imagination and creative thinking.

✓ **“Playing with blocks or legos”** It has been proven in practice that learning outcomes is better when it is done through blocks, cubes and lego games in order to give children an idea of shapes, colors and numbers in English. Playing with blocks, cubes and lego toys stimulates the child to think and develops his creative ability in doing something, as well as through these games the child has the opportunity to increase the vocabulary in English. Vocabulary in games is done by asking questions in English and conveying the basic concepts through instruction. The child learns to count and sort

through this game: **How many blocks are there? (how many cubes are there?) Shall we put the blue ones here? (Do we put a blue cube here?)** Learn the location of objects using prepositions: **in (inside), on (above), under (below), below (below), behind (behind), next to (next to)** . Gain an understanding of the units of measurement: **big, small, long, short**. Use the following words to instruct the child on what they are making: **Find the red block, please! (Pull the blue one, please!), Push them! (Push them!). !), Build the house, please! (Build a house!) Make the car, pleaser! (make a car!)**. Describes the objects and shapes the child makes: **square, rectangle, tower, house, castle, garden**

Through the type of educational activity "**Dressing**" children can be introduced to the fairy-tale heroes of the peoples of the world. When children are introduced to the characters of fairy tales, their costumes are worn and role-playing is done in English, and this activity increases the child's English vocabulary and expands the child's imagination and worldview. Through this educational activity, children learn words related to human body parts and clothing and have the opportunity to apply them in practice. Human body parts: **head, arms, hands, feet, legs, eyes...** Clothes: **dress jacket), shirt (boys jacket), t-shirt (t-shirt), shoes (shoes), slippers (slippers), cap (cap), belt (belt), gloves (gloves)...** The command is also given with emphasis on the body parts: **put your arms through here, tie this around your waist / wrist, put these on your feet) - first your right foot, then your left foot, then put this over your head.**

Children also enliven fairy-tale characters in their imagination, enter the image, and learn to use key words and phrases. This of course also helps to develop speaking skills by listening and understanding words in English and composing sentences from memorized words. **Describes the costumes of the protagonist (fairy (pari), princess (princess), pirate (robber), king (king), clown (clown))** and uses the words to dress : **put on (put on!), Zip up (lock the lock!), do the buttons up (unlock the buttons!), unbutton, unzip (unlock the lock).**

✓ **Animals and their sounds** are introduced to the world of animals and insects in English. Children also listen to various stories and tales involving animals. Learning about animals and their movements and sounds in English through pictures depicting colorful pictures of animals is also a fun activity for children. Pets **domestic animals: dog, cat, duck, cock, hen, chicken, cow...** Wild animals **wild animals: lion, tiger, wolf, rabbit, fox, snake, deer...** Learn the names of animals and insects in English **and train** children along with imitating their temperaments gives the child a world of pleasure.

<i>Hayvonot</i>	<i>Qanday tovush beradi</i>	<i>Tarjima</i>
Dogs	<i>bark</i>	<i>It</i>
Cats	<i>mew, purr, meow, hiss, yowl</i>	<i>Mushuk</i>
Caws	<i>moo, low</i>	<i>Sigir</i>
Ducks	<i>quack</i>	<i>O'rdak</i>
Frogs	<i>croak</i>	<i>Baqa</i>
Bees	<i>hum and buzz</i>	<i>Asalari</i>
Lions	<i>roar, growl</i>	<i>She'r</i>
Chicks	<i>cheep</i>	<i>Jo'ja</i>
Flies	<i>buzz, hum</i>	<i>Pashsha</i>
Birds	<i>chirrup, chirp, twitter, tweet, sing, whistle</i>	<i>Chumchug</i>
Wolves	<i>howl, cry, yell</i>	<i>Bo'rilar</i>

✓ **“Crafts” Handicraft:** a type of educational activity to make and decorate things. It is well known that a child is curious by nature, but it is also important to keep in mind that a child’s developmental process does not take place in the same way at the same time. Some children may have a different stage of development based on their social background, nature, and interests. Some children will be quiet and will not be able to join the crowd quickly, but their creativity will be well developed because they are observant. If such children are involved in the art of making things by hand, they will undoubtedly become real inventors of works of art.

When children are taught to make colorful things through manual labor, the child’s creative abilities develop, and when this activity is conducted in English, the vocabulary of the English language increases and the skills of listening comprehension and speaking also develop. So, this type of educational activity can be making shapes from pieces of paper, coloring shapes using paints, or making different things out of plasticine. Any process should not be free of English words and phrases.

The name of each tool and item should be communicated to children in English: **paint, paintbrush, crayon, marker card, paper, crepe paper (crepe paper), shiny paper, tissue paper, newspaper, glue, scissors, cotton wool, fabric (cloth), feathers (feathers)**. Instructions must be in English:

paint, draw, color, smudge, blow, copy, pour, make, cut, stick (paste), decorate, hang (it) up.

✓ **Sing a song.**

One of the kid’s favorite activities. Children tend to sing from a young age, and through singing, children not only gain vocabulary, but they also learn to pronounce words in tone. One of the most popular types of English songs sung among young children is “Rain, Rain go away”.

Rain, rain, go away

Come again another day

Daddy wants to play

Rain, rain go away...

If the educational game is carried out with the help of umbrellas, artificial clouds and artificial fire, children's activity will increase, the effectiveness of the result will increase.

✓ **Analyze children's participation in play**

It is necessary to ensure the active participation of children in educational activities, to pay special attention to each child and to encourage the child to learn something in this lesson. Praising successful children for their work also increases their motivation. But psychologists say that praise should be focused on the work done, not on the person. Because if praise is given to a person, it can lead the child to selfishness later. Praise for his work will ensure that any work will continue to be of quality and fast.

How children go to school and grow up with high goals largely depends on the family environment, the attention of the community and the upbringing in the preschool. The scientific observations and research presented in the article show that the fact that 70% of all information a person receives during his lifetime is received before the age of 6 shows the importance of preschool education in the development of a child's personality. At a meeting held by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on August 16, 2017 in order to determine measures for 100% coverage of children aged 5-6 in preschool education, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree "On Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan On the organization of the activities of the

Ministry ”. The purpose of the state requirements is to bring up a spiritually perfect and intellectually developed person in the preschool education system, taking into account the ongoing socio-economic reforms in the country, the best practices of foreign countries and scientific achievements and modern information and communication technologies. This means that the knowledge that children acquire at an early age, as our ancestors said, is "stoned". From this point of view, teaching foreign languages to children at an early age will make it easier for them to master language skills and abilities. Especially when this knowledge, skills and abilities are absorbed through various games and educational activities, the child develops foreign languages as naturally as his mother tongue. Educational games not only develop knowledge, skills and abilities in the child, but also ensure the child's healthy physical development, mental refreshment, strengthen self-confidence and contribute to the formation of social relations with others. gives mac.

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